

FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH ZINC OXIDE PIEZOELECTRIC NANOWIRES FOR STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING AND ENHANCED INTERLAMINAR STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

Fiber reinforced plastics (FRPs) laminated composites are used in many industries such as aerospace, automotive, civil, sporting goods, etc. Compared to traditional metals, FRP composites exhibit a high specific strength and stiffness making them ideal for high strength-low weight applications. The FRPs are prone to interlaminar delamination induced by different forces and this delamination can compromise the structural integrity and lead to critical failure. This study aims at growing nanoscale zinc oxide (ZnO) piezoelectric nanowires (NWs) on the surface of carbon fiber fabrics to act as sensors and actuators for structural health monitoring (SHM) applications and to increase the interlaminar shear strength. Results demonstrate a 20% and a 7% increase in strength and Young's modulus, respectively, compared to the raw (neat) composite. Furthermore, the composite exhibited 88% increase in the inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS). Our results also demonstrate that the impedance of the ZnO/FRP composite changes with delamination where the RMS value of the impedance increases with increasing severity of delamination damage.

1 INTRODUCTION

Load carrying structural composites, known as fiber reinforced polymers (FRPs), possess superior strength/weight and modulus/weight characteristics and comprise reinforcement of high performance fibers (e.g. glass, carbon, aramid and Kevlar) impregnated in polymer matrices (e.g. epoxy, thermoplastics, Nylon, polyester, etc.). Despite their attractive properties, FRPs are prone to interlaminar and intralaminar failures due to over loading, structure malfunction, overloading, etc. Failure and damage are quite complex for multilayered laminate composites due to their anisotropic behavior in comparison with isotropic metallic materials. With certain stacking sequences, the

laminates could easily delaminate across the thickness with overstress [1]. Another damage mechanism called transverse matrix cracking could also occur under tensile loading in stacking sequences that contain a lamina where the fibers at 90° from the direction of the load. These cracks propagate parallel to the fibers in the 90° layers, which are perpendicular to the principle direction (0°) of the composite, when a load is applied along the 0° direction. Delamination may lower the stiffness and strength of the composite while matrix cracking in the 90° layers causes stress concentrations in adjacent plies [1]. Traditional non-destructive testing (NDT) methods to detect delamination include computerized tomography (CT) scan, X-ray, eddy current, and coin tapping. These techniques are expensive, time consuming and labor intensive for large structures, impractical for an in-service condition, and typically strenuous to perform for parts that are inaccessible to the maintenance. Furthermore, the results interpretation may not be reliable as the inspections or measurements rely on practitioners' judgment based on their experiences, knowledge, and equipment. Carrying out most of these NDT techniques, disrupts the operation of the structures which is not practical for real-time in situ damage detection.

Considering the ever growing composites market size, there is growing and substantial interest in developing built-in damage detection platforms for composite structures [2–5]. Most of the techniques rely on passive sensor measurements to determine changes in the condition or environment of structures. Structural health monitoring (SHM) has received significant attention for autonomous damage detection in structures. Due to the benefits of SHM, such as reducing maintenance costs, preventing catastrophic failure, and improving safety and reliability, it has received a considerable amount of attention from both industrial sectors and government agencies encompassing many engineering fields, such as bridge monitoring [2], pipeline inspection [3], aging aircraft [4, 5], and space operation vehicles [6, 7]. Generally, SHM can be divided into three fundamental steps: 1) Detection: damage existence and location evaluation, 2) Diagnosis: damage assessment with classification and extent estimation, and 3) Prognosis: prediction of remaining useful life and further management. Within SHM, there are different approaches such as vibration based methods [8-10], impedance based method [11-14], and the guided wave propagation method [4, 15-21]. Researchers such as Kabeya et al. [22, 23], Zagrai et al. [24-26], Rizzo et al. [27, 28], Park and Inman [13, 29, 30], and Sohn et al. [31, 32] have made notable contributions to the area of guided-wave and impedance-based structural health monitoring strategies.

The impedance based method generally utilizes piezoceramic (PZT) patches or wafers bonded internally or externally to a structure. Liang et al. [33] showed that the mechanical impedance of the structure is coupled to the electrical impedance of the PZT actuator. By measuring changes in the electrical impedance of the PZT, any changes in the mechanical impedance can be detected due to the electromechanical coupling of the PZT [34, 35]. Since the imaginary part of the admittance is more sensitive to temperature variations, the real part of the impedance or admittance is typically used for structural health monitoring. This method typically utilizes relatively high frequencies (between 30 kHz and 400 kHz) through the collocated PZT actuator and sensor. As a result of the higher frequencies, the system is more sensitive to minor changes than methods such as vibration-based techniques. Other advantages of the method include low power requirements for excitation (less than 1 Volt), the possibility to be applied to complex structures, and no dependence on an analytical model for implementation.

Many remedies were suggested to eliminate delamination by enhancing the FRP fiber/matrix interface. In particular, zinc oxide (ZnO) nanowires (NWs) can be grown on the fiber surface to enhance the interface between the fibers and the matrix. Zinc oxide is a very intriguing material due to its intrinsic semiconductor and piezoelectric properties which make it well-suited for a variety of applications from solar cells, sensors, structural applications, to energy harvesting devices [36-39]. The origin of the piezoelectricity in ZnO stems from its crystal structure, where the oxygen atoms and zinc atoms are tetrahedrally bonded. In such a non-centrosymmetric structure, the center of positive charge and negative charge can be relocated upon applying external pressure leading to lattice

distortion. This displacement yields local dipole moments, thus a macroscopic dipole moments emerges over the whole crystal.

While investigators have demonstrated ZnO piezoelectric on small substrates and cellulose fibers [40], no work has been done demonstrating large scale implementation in fiber reinforced composites. Therefore, the objective of the present work is to advance the state of the art in smart composite technology. Specifically we propose to grow nanoscale ZnO piezoelectric nanowires on the surface of carbon fibers, manufacture a layered composite based on the hybrid reinforcement, and then test the feasibility of the ZnO NWs to act as a transducer for structural health monitoring and as an interfacial strengthening mechanism. Mechanical tests are performed to measure the effect of the surface grown ZnO on the strength, stiffness and interlaminar shear strength of the composite. Impedance analysis measurements are carried out to access the sensitivity of ZnO composites to induced damage.

2 MATERIALS AND FABRICATION

ZnO nanowires are grown onto high-strength sized polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based plain-woven carbon fabric (AS2C-Hexcel Inc.) with 3k bundles by presputtering a thin layer (75 nm) of ZnO using high vacuum magnetron sputtering system (ATC Orion high vacuum sputtering system, AJA International, Inc.) to provide seeds for growth initiation. The fabric is then soaked in a 40 mmol mixture of zinc acetate hexahydrate and Hexamethylenetetramine (Sigma-Aldrich, Inc.) at 85°C for 4 hours for ZnO NWs growth. To establish reference samples, another ZnO sputtered fabric and bare carbon fabric (without ZnO sputtering) were immersed in hot DI water bath for 4 hours at 85 °C to mimic the hydrothermal experimental conditions of the sample with ZnO growth. Scanning electron microscopy (LEO (Zeiss) 1550 field emission SEM) was utilized to study the size (length, diameter) and morphology (shape, dispersion) of the grown ZnO NWs.

After completing the growth step, the three fiber configurations (growth, sputtered and bare) were utilized to manufacture three separate sets of 4-layers laminate composites via vacuum assisted hand lay-up process. The matrix material used for the composite preparation comprised two components thermosetting epoxy: Epon 815C (resin) and Epikure 3282 (curing agent) provided by Miller-Stephenson Chemical Company, Inc. All the obtained composites lamina were cured at room temperature for 4 hours and post cured in the oven for 2 hours at 100 °C. The laminates were cut into strips with size of 0.5"×5.0" according to the ASTM standard D3039/D3039M-08. The tensile tests were performed via an Instron® 4400 load frame. The strain was measured using an extensometer from MTS, Inc. The strain rate during the tensile test was set to 0.5 mm/min.

To assess the influence of the ZnO nanowires on the interlaminar properties of the composite, the short beam test (SBS), was adopted to characterize the ‘apparent’ interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of FRPs. The test is manifested by a rectangular cross-section short beam specimen loaded in three-point bending to initiate an interlaminar failure. The tests were conducted at the displacement rate of 1 mm/min in accordance with the ASTM-D2344 specifications. Small span-to-thickness ($S/h=2$) was adopted to induce high interlaminar shear in the test specimen. A different set of samples were prepared to comply with the laminate symmetry requirements for the SBS test, the SBS specimen consisted of eight alternating layers $[0^0,45^0]_4$ of carbon fibers polymer composites. Five different samples were tested for each composite based the five aforementioned fiber surface treatments.

To investigate the SHM capabilities of the hybrid composite, we prepared different beam samples after the step of growing ZnO as follows: we sputtered a 250 nm thick layer of copper on top of the ZnO/carbon fabric hybrid to ensure the piezoelectric charges collection from the single ZnO nanowires. The introduced copper layer had the additional

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of a segment of the fabricated structural health monitoring device.

role of establishing a Schottky rectification effect in the circuit necessary for the electric power generation mechanism. To prevent short circuit in the device, a breather ply layer was inserted to separate the opposing faces of the carbon fabric. This layer ensured complete electrical insulation between the two electrodes attached each to the conductive carbon fabric with a silver paste. To verify that the generated electrical output resulted only from the piezoelectric properties of the ZnO nanowires, a reference configuration was prepared by sputtering a 250 nm copper layer on top of the carbon fabric as shown in Figure 1. Finally, two layers were stacked to form a laminate using vacuum assisted pressing, and attach electrodes to the ohmic contacts. Finally we induced delamination damage at different lengths to the composite beam to investigate its SHM performance.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical testing and properties

Figure 2 shows the morphology and the coverage quality of the ZnO NWs grown on the surface of the PAN carbon fabric. The NWs grew radially on the fibers surface with almost identical morphology; comparable lengths (1.6-1.7 μm) and diameters within 100 nm (see inset image in Figure 1).

Figure 2. Image of ZnO NWs grown on surface of PAN carbon fabric

The tensile strengths and Young's moduli for the different composites configurations are shown in Figure 3(a). The strength of the fibers and thus the composite has decreased as a consequence of exposing the carbon fibers to the hydrothermal conditions. On the contrary, depositing a thin amorphous ZnO layer increased the strength by 18.8% irrespective of the hydrothermal conditions.

Growing ZnO NWs on the carbon fibers surface yielded a 20.5% increase in the strength compared to the reference composite based on dry carbon fibers. Hence, growing ZnO NWs counterbalanced the negative effects of the hydrothermal growth conditions. Furthermore, coating the carbon fibers with zinc oxide NWs ensured gradual load transfer between the stiff carbon fibers and the epoxy matrix which avoids stress concentration at the interface. Figure 3 also indicates that soaking the carbon fibers in the hot mixture did not affect their stiffness. While, depositing 80 nm amorphous ZnO layer enhanced the stiffness of the corresponding composite by 16.6% irrespective of the hydrothermal exposure. Grafting ZnO NWs on the carbon fibers surface improved the composite strength by 7.8% compared to the reference composite based on dry PAN fibers, a decrease of 7.4% can be noticed in the stiffness compared to the composite based on ZnO sputtered fibers. This drop can be attributed to the morphology of the NWs that allows them to bend slightly during the loading

Figure 3 (a) The Young's modulus and tensile strength and (b) the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of FRPs based on the different surface treatments of the PAN carbon fibers.

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The results of the interlaminar shear strength test are summarized in Figure 3(b). The results revealed that saturating the carbon fibers in hot growth mixture degraded the ILSS by 9.0%. The ZnO sputtered then soaked configuration encountered only 2.0% reduction in the ILSS in comparison to the raw fibers. On the contrary, coating the carbon fibers with ZnO layer yielded 55.0% increase in the ILSS; which can be attributed to enhanced interlaminar adhesion. The strong adhesion of the ZnO layer to the fibers is caused by the electrostatic interaction as demonstrated by Galan et al [22]. As shown in Figure 3(b), growing ZnO NWs on PAN fibers surfaces improved the ILSS of the composite structure by 88.0% compared to the baseline composite specimen prepared with neat fibers without any surface treatment. This enhancement can be explained by the morphology and the comparatively higher aspect ratio and the added surface area of the grown ZnO nanowires which provide increased adhesion area and promote the mechanical interlocking at the NWs/epoxy interface.

3.2 Impulse response and impedance measurements

Tests were performed in the Aerospace Structures and Materials Laboratory (ASML) to evaluate the output response of the hybrid ZnO composite samples with an applied impulse voltage. As shown in Figure 5A, the composite beam is mounted in a cantilever configuration and the tip displacement is measured with a Polytec laser vibrometer. Using a simple push button switch, impulse voltages with increasing magnitude are applied to the sample using a power supply and leads attached at each end of the sample. As shown in Figure 4, the ZnO beam undergoes a ring down response with each impulse voltage and the amplitude increases with increasing applied voltage. These results indicate a piezoelectric coupling exists in the composite beam.

Figure 4 Tip displacement of ZnO sample with increasing impulse voltages

Figure 5 (A) Test setup for measuring response of ZnO sample with voltage impulse, (B) sample showing final damaged state (Damage 3 in Figure 7), and (C) samples having varying levels of delamination (Left to right: 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 100%)

Impedance testing is performed using a custom National Instruments PXI modular impedance analyzer. The system uses a NI PXI-5402 100 MS/s 20 MHz function generator for excitation and a NI PXIe-5122 100 MS/s digitizer for data collection. Before each series of tests, the system is calibrated using a known impedance load. As shown in Figure 6, there is good agreement between the custom NI analyzer and an Agilent E4980A Precision LCR meter for a PZT attached to a beam. These results took more than two hours to collect with the LCR meter and only one minute with the NI system, thus significantly decreasing the time for testing.

Figure 6 Comparison of custom NI impedance analyzer with Agilent E4980A Precision LCR Meter

Tests were performed for a ZnO composite sample with increasing levels of damage. Shown in Figure 5B is the sample after the last damage was induced in the sample. Impedance measurements were first recorded across different frequency ranges for the pristine sample to determine a baseline case. Damage in the form of a slit is created in the sample using a razor blade and impedance measurements are recorded after each increase in the size of the damage. Shown in Figure 7 are the results from these tests. The effect of the damage on the magnitude and phase of the impedance is clearly seen where the magnitude decreases as the size of the damage increases.

Figure 7 Impedance of ZnO sample (Figure 5B) with increasing levels of damage

Next impedance measurements were recorded for ZnO composite samples having varying levels of pre-imposed delaminations (Figure 5C). The pre-imposed delaminations were introduced using PTFE strips inserted between the two carbon fiber plies. The sample on the left has 0% delamination (no strip) and the width of PTFE strip increases with each sample from left to right. For example, 50% delamination denotes that the width of the PTFE strip is half the width of the beam and 100% indicates that the strip is the same width as the beam. Shown in Figure 8 are the results from the five samples with varying amounts of pre-imposed delaminations. As seen in the results, the impedance magnitude and phase increases with increasing delamination levels, except for the 50% delamination sample. This can be clearly seen in the RMS values of the impedance magnitudes shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8 Impedance of ZnO samples (Figure 5C) with varying levels of delamination

Figure 9 RMS values of impedance of ZnO samples (Figure 5C) with varying levels of delamination

4 CONCLUSIONS

Fiber reinforced composites with zinc oxide piezoelectric nanowires are promising materials for structural health monitoring applications. The effect of ZnO NWs growth is significant on the mechanical properties. While the hydrothermal exposure to the synthesis environment affected the carbon fibers negatively in terms reduced stiffness and strength, grafting ZnO NWs improved the tensile properties. The NWs growth contribution was more pronounced for the interlaminar shear strength (ILLS) which demonstrated the enhancement of interfacial adhesion between the carbon fibers and the NWs from one side, and the NWs and the epoxy matrix from the other side. Impedance measurements were recorded for ZnO composite samples having varying levels of damage. The results demonstrate that the impedance of the composites is sensitive to damage, and the magnitude changes depending on damage type and location. Thus, the ZnO/FRP composites benefit from the ZnO NWs both by improving the mechanical properties and providing an electromechanical coupling that can be advantageous for structural health monitoring.

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